

Mizo traditional water management systems and water resistivity survey in Lungsen, Mizoram

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Abstract: The Mizo indigenous people have their own way several entities in managing their livelihood. Water management system is one such knowledge passed down from their ancestors for sustainable livelihoods. Rain and monsoon fed springs, rivers and streams have their sacred place amongst the Mizos. In the study, integrating with modern science a collaboration of geology, geobotanical and geophysical study was conducted using Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) method in Lungsen village of Mizoram to search for gaps in the water management systems of the village during the post-monsoon season.

Keywords: Geology, water, survey, resistivity method, Mizoram.

Introduction: Mizoram is located on the Chittagong-Mizoram-Tripura fold-thrust belt of India, Burma and Bangladesh between 21°56'N - 24°31N and 92°16' E-93°26E longitude covering an area of 21,081 square kilometres. The international boundary with Bangladesh is over 318 kilometres and with Myanmar over 404 kilometres. It became the 23rd state of India on the 20th February, 1987. Aizawl, the capital of Mizoram is selected for the study. It is located in the northern part of Mizoram and is situated on a ridge and is geographically located at 23°43'59N and 92°43'00E longitude. According to the Census of India's report 2011, the capital Aizawl district is the home to 4,00,309 people. Prior to the British colonial powers arrival in Mizoram any sort of formal education was absent amongst the Mizos. Mizo traditional knowledge systems on water and its management were intrinsic in their society and occupations. In association to their social and work lives, rains were named accordingly with each rain have their impact and results on their agrarian economy as the Mizos were not reluctant to work on their fields even during rain and storms as they believe it as their crops and fruits will be bountiful. Also, poets composed songs which depict the lives in the fields. It is impossible to separate traditional knowledge with the socio-economic lives with the advent of science and modern technology.

Indigenous knowledge is a network of knowledge, beliefs and traditions intended to preserve, communicate and contextualize indigenous relationships with culture and landscape over time (Bruchac, 2014). enumerated that indigenous knowledge supply needs of the community from natural sources and became valuable source of practices for sustainable development of all societies (Khodomoradi & Abedi, 2011). Agriculture of Mizo is immensely depending upon the rainfall and the knowledge of weather and climate held by local and tribal communities can play significant role in agriculture (Chinlapianga, 2011). In areas like the

East Kawlchaw Watershed in Saiha, communities also use bamboo stakes to regulate water flow and prevent soil erosion, complementing terrace cultivation practices (Sahoo *et al.*, 2018). Also, Traditional seed preservation, for instance, involves storing heirloom crop varieties in bamboo containers or woven baskets, ensuring genetic diversity and resilience to climate variability (Lalfakzuala *et al.*, 2015). Agriculture, sustaining over 60% of Mizoram's population, is particularly vulnerable. Jhum cultivation, a traditional practice, faces challenges from shortened crop cycles, declining soil fertility, and rising pest infestations, leading to lower yields (Karuppusamy *et al.*, 2021).

Study area: Lungsen is a small yet culturally vibrant village located in the southern part of Mizoram, near the international border with Bangladesh (Figure 1). It falls under the Lunglei district and is surrounded by rolling hills, dense forests, and scenic landscapes that are characteristic of Mizoram's natural beauty. Though modest in size and population, Lungsen plays an important role in the local administration and community life of the region. The village is predominantly inhabited by the Mizos who follow rich cultural traditions and customs passed down through generations. Community cooperation and strong social bonds are central to life in Lungsen, reflecting the broader Mizo principle of "Tlawmngaihna," which emphasizes selflessness and service to others. Agriculture is the primary occupation of the residents. Many families practice jhum cultivation (shifting cultivation), growing crops such as rice, maize, and vegetables. The fertile hills and favorable climate support farming activities, although the terrain can make large-scale agriculture challenging. Small-scale trade and government services also contribute to the local economy. Road connectivity links Lungsen to nearby towns, but transportation can be affected by weather conditions, especially during the monsoon season. The geology of the study area is made up of arenaceous and argillaceous rocks. These rocks constitute the Surma group of rocks. They are thickly bedded sandstones, shales and mudstones of various stratigraphic horizons. The geology of Mizoram is part of the Indo-Myanmar Range and represents a young fold mountain system formed during the Tertiary period. Located in the northeastern state of Mizoram, the region belongs to the Assam-Arakan Basin and was shaped by the collision of the Indian Plate with the Burmese Plate. This tectonic interaction caused intense folding and faulting, producing the north-south trending hill ranges that characterize the state. The rock formations are predominantly sedimentary and of Miocene age. They consist mainly of sandstone, shale, siltstone, and mudstone deposited in ancient marine environments. The important stratigraphic units include the Surma Group (Bhuban and Bokabil formations), Barail Group and Tipam Group. These rocks are arranged in tightly packed anticlines and synclines, giving rise to parallel ridges and valleys. Mizoram is seismically active and falls under Seismic Zone VI prepared by the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) indicating a very high earthquake risk. The folded structures also create favorable conditions for petroleum and natural gas accumulation. Overall, the geology of Mizoram reflects active tectonics, young sedimentary formations, and a structurally complex mountain landscape formed by plate convergence.

Figure 1: Lungsen village and its location with co-ordinates in Mizoram

Methodology: The Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) method is a Geophysical survey method (2D geophysical) where the vertical variation of different electrical resistivity in the sub-surface (deep inside the earth) is measured to determine the amount of water underneath the preferred study area. This survey works on the principle that electric current is passed down inside the earth using two current electrodes and thus by measuring the potential difference (resulting voltage) between two electrodes. During the survey, the center of the array (electrode) remains fixed throughout the survey. Investigating deeper layers is done by expanding the spacing i.e., the distance between the electrodes is gradually increased. With increased spacing, the current penetrates deeper depths of the earth and thus providing a vertical profile of resistivity beneath the center point.

Results and Conclusion: The value of the topsoil resistivity ranges between several ohm-m. The range of resistivity values suggests dissimilarities in the composition of materials constituting the topsoil in the study area (Figure 2). The resistivity of weathered layer has a low range of values. The resistivity suggests lithology in the suite of sandy clay, clayey sand and shale/clay to be widespread.

Figure 2: Pseudo cross-section from Vertical Electrical Sounding profile of Lungsen village

The low values recorded could be attributed to the clay content in the aquifers and the fact that the degree of hydraulic conductivity between the fractures is low. It is recommended that, the study area where overburden layer is relatively thick and has favorably low resistivity values should be considered for groundwater development.

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